

K'iche' (Quiché)

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Entered by Emily Pitek, Human Relations Area Files

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** Secondary Source entry, prepared from a literature review by a Ph.D. RA*

Entry tags: Syncretic Religions, Central American Religions, Religious Group

This entry focuses on the K'iche' living in the town of Chichicastenango, Guatemala, around the time of 1930. The principal ethnographic authority, Bunzel (1952), indicated that at this time, Chichicastenango remained relatively isolated from intensive industrialization, European Colonialism, and Christianity. Although the arrival of European (primarily Spanish) colonists brought elements of Catholicism and political changes, the traditional K'iche' cultural and religious beliefs and practices remained. Consequently, K'iche' religious beliefs were somewhat syncretic, blending and incorporating aspects of Catholicism with traditional beliefs. Bunzel (1952:163) described that the Church and State are one in Chichicastenango, and "the problems of the individual soul, of life and death, sin and salvation, the relationship of man to the supernatural and to his own conscience are worked out through other institutions. The Church is primarily political--a state temple in which the rules and their surrogates discharge their religious obligations to the commonwealth." In addition to church officials, the chuchqajau serves as a religious practitioner and specializes as a professional diviner, performing ceremonies for pay. These ceremonies occur during major turning points in life, such as baptism, marriage, and death. Other events in life have ceremonial aspects as well, such as building a house, planting and harvesting, and selling land. Ceremonies typically include a feast for the officiating individual and offerings to supernatural beings (Bunzel, 1952:84). Larger, communal ceremonies occur during fiestas, which mark significant holidays and are important to religious, social, and political aspects of K'iche' culture. Because religion permeates all aspects of life, this entry considers the religious group to be coterminous with K'iche' society itself.

Date Range: 1910 CE - 1940 CE

Region: Town of Chichicastenango

Region tags: North America, Mesoamerica and the Caribbean

Town of Chichicastenango, Guatemala, ca. 1930

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Divale, W. 2004. Codebook of Variables for the Standard Cross-Cultural Sample. *World Cultures: The Journal of Cross-Cultural and Comparative Research*.
- Source 2: Tuden, A. & Marshall, C. (Oct., 1972). Political organization: Cross-cultural codes 4. *Ethnology*, 11(4), 436-464.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=nw10-001>

– Source 1 Description: Bunzel, Ruth Leah. 1952. "Chichicastenango: A Guatemalan Village." In *Publications of the American Ethnological Society*, xxvi, 438. Locust Valley, N.Y.: J. J. Augustin.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: Although relatively isolated, Chichicastenango showed evidence of influence from European (primarily Spanish) colonialism and Christianity. See Bunzel, 1952 p.v-vii. "It is probably not an accident that there are a number of German, Dutch and German-American priests in the populous [K'iche'] towns of the Highlands. This phenomenon is probably not unrelated to the economic hold of the Germans on the whole country, which has broken down at the top, where it is giving way to American control. Thus, successive waves of imperialism, Spanish, German, American, beat about the bases of [K'iche'] strongholds. Directly, they have no effect on [K'iche'] life. The [K'iche'] makes no distinction between the Ladino [non-indigenous Guatemalans], the German and the American...What is of importance in its indirect effect on [K'iche'] civilization is the fact that the Ladino [non-indigenous Guatemalans] is no longer the master of his country" (Bunzel, 1952:13).

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 1649, Frequency of Internal Warfare (resolved rating), internal warfare seems to be absent or rare (Ember and Ember, 1992; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 1650, Frequency of External Warfare (resolved rating), external warfare seems to be absent or rare (Ember and Ember, 1992; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

Notes: "It is baptism, with its Church ceremony and its equally important civic ceremony conducted by an official patron of children, that establishes the child's position as a member of the community" (Bunzel, 1952:162).

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– No

Notes: No, group membership is established during the ritual of baptism (see Bunzel, 1952:162).

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– No

Notes: No, group membership is established during the ritual of baptism (see Bunzel, 1952:162).

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

Notes: No, group membership is established during the ritual of baptism (see Bunzel, 1952:162).

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

Notes: No, group membership is established during the ritual of baptism (see Bunzel, 1952:162).

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

Notes: No, group membership is established during the ritual of baptism (see Bunzel, 1952:162).

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– Yes

Notes: "It is baptism, with its Church ceremony and its equally important civic ceremony conducted by an official patron of children, that establishes the child's position as a member of the community" (Bunzel, 1952:162).

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– I don't know

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: "It should be recalled that the church buildings and land belong to the municipality and are maintained by public service. In Chichicastenango, Church and State are one. The problems of the individual soul, of life and death, sin and salvation, the relationship of man to the supernatural and to his own conscience are worked out through other institutions. The Church is primarily political – a state temple in which the rulers and their surrogates discharge their religious obligations to the commonwealth" (Bunzel, 1952:163).

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– Yes

Notes: "The functions of the two alcaldes are largely ritualistic and judicial. Their role in ecclesiastical affairs, especially in the conduct of affairs in the *cofradías*, has already been stressed. For the rest they are judges of first appeal in all internal disputes between [K'iche'], disputes over land and other property, regulation of domestic affairs, small criminal offenses that do not involve Ladinos. They are responsible for carrying out executive orders relating to [K'iche'] affairs" (Bunzel, 1952:175).

↳ Polity provides preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax, exemption)

– Yes

Notes: "The sacristans of the church form a privileged class. There are about thirty of them. They are placed in this service by their fathers when they are still children, and they grow up in it. In recognition of their service their families are exempt from all taxes and work levies" (Bunzel, 1952: 85).

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– I don't know

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 25000

Notes: See Bunzel, 1952:12

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– I don't know

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Note: a Christian priest is present, but this individual is not K'iche'. "The Church in the highlands is [K'iche'], and a great mechanism of [K'iche'] solidarity. In Chichicastenango the [K'iche'] municipality holds the title to the church, and holds itself responsible for its maintenance. The resident priest there is a German by birth and a citizen of the United States by adoption: (Bunzel, 1952:13). "Of all the professions that of *chuchqajau* is the most important and the most highly formalized. The *chuchqajau* has supernatural powers; he is a diviner, sorcerer and mediator before the gods and the ancestors in all the crises of life. He is not, strictly speaking, a priest, for his relation to the supernatural is not such as to make his services in any ceremony indispensable. His position is that of an expert in occult science who performs ceremonies for others for pay" (Bunzel, 1952:79).

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– Yes

Notes: "Of all the professions that of chuchqajau is the most important and the most highly formalized. The chuchqajau has supernatural powers; he is a diviner, sorcerer and mediator before the gods and the ancestors in all the crises of life" (Bunzel, 1952:79).

↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in past lives:

– No

Notes: See the questions below for more information.

↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in the current life:

– Yes

Notes: "To become a chuchqajau one must have a call which is manifested in dreams, through sickness and by divination...The initiation ceremonies extend over a period of 180 days, during which time there are many rituals and sacrifices, and instructions of the novice by the older man who initiates him, in the fundamentals of his calling" (Bunzel, 1952:79).

↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from another human (e.g. teacher):

– Yes

Notes: "To become a chuchqajau one must have a call which is manifested in dreams, through sickness and by divination...The initiation ceremonies extend over a period of 180 days, during which time there are many rituals and sacrifices, and instructions of the novice by the older man who initiates him, in the fundamentals of his calling. This instruction covers the arts of divination, the symbolism of the calendar, and the essentials of ritual" (Bunzel, 1945:79).

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– I don't know

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– I don't know

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Notes: "...the Popol Buj, that extraordinary compendium of Quiché mythology and history, perhaps the most important literary monument of the ancient Highland civilization" (Bunzel, 1952:vi).

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

Notes: Bunzel, 1952:vi

↳ Are they oral:

– No

Notes: Bunzel, 1952:vi

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Notes: "The plaza is dominated by the church, a huge whitewashed stone structure, built in its present form in the eighteenth century, and rebuilt several times since that time. The original church where Ximenes preached and where, presumably, the author of the Popul Buj labored, is now the sacristy. The present church, like the sacristy, is a splendid example of Spanish Colonial architecture, amply proportioned, with immensely thick walls, heavily buttressed" (Bunzel, 1952:3).

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

Notes: See questions below for more details.

↳ Devotional markers:

– Yes

Notes: "The shrine Turqa' with its famous carved idol, its stone crosses, mysterious stone rings, and ancient mullers. The shrine itself is raised a few inches from the level of the ground and bordered with stones. At the back is a low wall of stones, against which the sacred objects stand. In front and lower down is a hearth for burning copal, and farther off, another hearth" (Bunzel, 1952:261).

Is iconography present:

– I don't know

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of pilgrimages.

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: See Bunzel, 1952:152

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: "The Quichés have never accepted Christian ideas of the after life although they invoke the 'Blessed Spirits in Purgatory' among other Christian powers. Their adherence to ideas of purgatory, hell and heaven, and even to the concept of rewards and punishment in an after life is perfunctory and has none of the vitality of the aboriginal beliefs about the dead as the upholders of moral law" (Bunzel, 1952:269). "Although there is no heaven and no hell the spirits have definite places of residence, or rather places where the living can meet them. These places are the house, the church and the cemetery" (Bunzel, 1952:270).

Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: "Although there is no heaven and no hell the spirits have definite places of residence, or rather places where the living can meet them. These places are the house, the church and the cemetery" (Bunzel, 1952:270).

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of a belief in reincarnation.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Notes: The deceased are placed in coffins for burial in a cemetery (see Bunzel, 1952:150).

Cremation:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of cremation.

Mummification:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of mummification.

↳ Interment:

– Yes

Notes: The deceased are placed in coffins for burial in a cemetery (see Bunzel, 1952:150).

↳ Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):

– No

Notes: The corpse is presumed to be extended within the coffin.

↳ Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):

– Yes

Notes: The corpse is presumed to be extended within the coffin.

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of cannibalism.

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating that corpses would be exposed to the elements.

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating that corpses were fed to animals.

↳ Secondary burial:

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 1850, Secondary Bone/Body Treatment (Original Scale), "secondary contact with the body or bones of the deceased does not occur" (Schroeder, 2001; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of co-sacrifices in burials.

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

Notes: "When he [the deceased father of a house] is dressed they put him in the coffin, and they put in with him all the things which he had, his sandals, hat, his cups from which he drank his coffee, his knives and shears, and all his old clothing – all that he possessed" (Bunzel, 1952:150).

Personal effects:

– Yes

Notes: "When he [the deceased father of a house] is dressed they put him in the coffin, and they put in with him all the things which he had, his sandals, hat, his cups from which he drank his coffee, his knives and shears, and all his old clothing – all that he possessed" (Bunzel, 1952:150).

Valuable items:

– I don't know

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Notes: Formal burial practices are described in Bunzel, 1952 pp.150-153.

In cemetery:

– Yes

Notes: Cemeteries are described in Bunzel, 1952:150.

Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating the deceased were interred in domestic spaces.

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: "With no mythology to guide us we are forced to rely on ritual, especially the long invocations that open prayers, for our knowledge of the gods. The most striking feature of these invocations is the inclusion of God, Christ and the saints among the diversified forces of nature, divine law, and the masters of human activities" (Bunzel, 1952: 265).

A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 238, High Gods, a high god is "present, active, and

specifically supportive of human morality" (Murdock, 1962-71; Retrieved from Divale, 2004). The Christian God is present, but not described in detail by the principal ethnographic authority. The K'iche' religion is syncretic, pulling from both Christianity and traditional, indigenous belief systems.

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

Notes: Monarchy is not present.

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

Notes: Monarchy is not present.

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– Yes

Notes: Other supernatural beings are present, see questions below for more information on these beings.

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Notes: "Although there is no heaven and no hell the spirits have definite places of residence, or rather places where the living can meet them. These places are the house, the church and the cemetery" (Bunzel, 1952:270).

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– No

Notes: "No one mentioned seeing ghosts" (Bunzel, 1952:271).

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Notes: "There is no belief that the mental life of the spirits differs in any way from that of the living except in being more knowing and more powerful" (Bunzel, 1952:269).

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: "As former owners of the house and land, the ancestors, along with the 'idols', enforce social order within the house" (Bunzel, 1952:269).

↳ Human spirits can reward:

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits can punish:

– Yes

Notes: "Adultery, theft, drunkenness, and neglect of ritual obligations are other 'sins committed within the house' which the ancestors punish by sending sickness or death, or by loss of property" (Bunzel, 1952:269).

↳ Human spirits have memory of life:

– Yes

Notes: "The dead experience all the emotions of the living; they suffer from ambition, envy, greed, malice, and vengefulness which they take out on the living or on those of their fellow ghosts who were their enemies or enemies of their families during their lives" (Bunzel, 1952:269).

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

Notes: "The dead experience all the emotions of the living..." (Bunzel, 1952:269).

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: "The dead experience all the emotions of the living; they suffer from ambition, envy, greed, malice, and vengefulness which they take out on the living or on those of their fellow ghosts who were their enemies or enemies of their families during their lives" (Bunzel, 1952:269).

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: "Phenomena of nature. Our father, Sun, (rarely 'our mother, Moon'); the cardinal points, the cloudy firmament, the cold wind (the destructive force of the world), the 'green shoulder, yellow shoulder of the world' (the procreative powers of the earth), the watchers by day and the watchers by night; those who go about in the sky and on the earth and under the earth; the mountains and volcanoes and other local spirits" (Bunzel, 1952:266). "Of all the forces that influence man's fate the most inaccessible and arbitrary is man's own soul. The form and substance of his in some animal or sacred objects - some snake, or bird or wild beast that wanders in the forest, or some stone idol that is buried in the earth. This creature is his destiny [animal]" (Bunzel, 1952:274).

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– I don't know

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: "Phenomena of nature. Our father, Sun, (rarely 'our mother, Moon'); the cardinal points, the cloudy firmament, the cold wind (the destructive force of the world), the 'green shoulder, yellow shoulder of the world' (the procreative powers of the earth), the watchers by day and the watchers by night; those who go about in the sky and on the earth and under the earth; the mountains and volcanoes and other local spirits" (Bunzel, 1952:266).

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: "The saints. The Eternal Father; Christ in glory (the image in the church), the source of tradition; Christ in Calvario (the image in Calvario), the saint of sinners; The 'Patrons of the Village,' Santo Tomás, San José, San Sebastian in the cofradías; Santa Ana, patron of mid wives; San Juan Bautista (nuestra luz y estrella), the guardian of personal destiny; San Pedro (qui tiene la llave), patron of divinens; La Santa Cruz, symbol of the Earth; all the saints in the altars of the church and in the cofradías; the 'thirteen-fourteen angels and apostles;' and the 'angels who go about in the cloudy firmament'" (Bunzel, 1952:266).

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: "With no mythology to guide us we are forced to rely on ritual, especially the long invocations that open prayers, for our knowledge of the gods. The most striking feature of these invocations is the inclusion of God, Christ and the saints among the diversified forces of nature, divine law, and the masters of human activities" (Bunzel, 1952: 265).

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– I don't know

Notes: The organization of supernatural beings is not explicitly described, but supernatural beings seem to be grouped by various types (e.g., ancestor, God, saints). However, it is unclear if this organization is created by the principal ethnographic authority (Bunzel, 1952) or K'iche' informants.

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Notes: "Quarrels within the family and the resulting vindictiveness are the chief source of offense to the ancestors. Adultery, theft, drunkenness, and neglect of ritual obligations are other 'sins committed

within the house' which the ancestors punish by sending sickness or death, or by loss of property" (Bunzel, 1952:269).

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

Notes: "Quarrels within the family and the resulting vindictiveness are the chief source of offense to the ancestors. Adultery, theft, drunkenness, and neglect of ritual obligations are other 'sins committed within the house' which the ancestors punish by sending sickness or death, or by loss of property" (Bunzel, 1952:269).

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

Notes: "Adultery, theft, drunkenness, and neglect of ritual obligations are other 'sins committed within the house' which the ancestors punish by sending sickness or death, or by loss of property" (Bunzel, 1952:269).

↳ Adultery:

– Yes

Notes: "Adultery, theft, drunkenness, and neglect of ritual obligations are other 'sins committed within the house' which the ancestors punish by sending sickness or death, or by loss of property" (Bunzel, 1952:269).

↳ Incest:

– I don't know

↳ Other sexual practices:

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– Yes

Notes: "Quarrels within the family and the resulting vindictiveness are the chief source of offense to the ancestors" (Bunzel, 1952:269).

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Yes

Notes: "Adultery, theft, drunkenness, and neglect of ritual obligations are other 'sins committed within the house' which the ancestors punish by sending sickness or death, or by loss of property" (Bunzel, 1952:269).

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

Notes: "Adultery, theft, drunkenness, and neglect of ritual obligations are other 'sins committed within the house' which the ancestors punish by sending sickness or death, or by loss of property" (Bunzel, 1952:269).

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: Drunkenness

Notes: "Adultery, theft, drunkenness, and neglect of ritual obligations are other 'sins committed within the house' which the ancestors punish by sending sickness or death, or by loss of property" (Bunzel, 1952:269).

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

Notes: See questions below for more details regarding supernatural punishment.

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Notes: See questions below for more details regarding the cause of supernatural punishment.

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

Notes: The high god is not described as causing supernatural punishment. Rather, ancestors are the supernatural beings said to cause punishment. See questions below for more details.

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: Ancestors are the primary supernatural beings causing supernatural punishment. "Quarrels within the family and the resulting vindictiveness are the chief source of offense to the ancestors. Adultery, theft, drunkenness, and neglect of ritual obligations are other 'sins committed within the house' which the ancestors punish by sending sickness or death, or by loss of property" (Bunzel, 1952:269).

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural punishment occurs for various reasons. See questions below for more detail.

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

Notes: "Adultery, theft, drunkenness, and neglect of ritual obligations are other 'sins committed within the house' which the ancestors punish by sending sickness or death, or by loss of property" (Bunzel, 1952:269).

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

Notes: "Quarrels within the family and the resulting vindictiveness are the chief source of offense to the ancestors. Adultery, theft, drunkenness, and neglect of ritual obligations are other 'sins committed within the house' which the ancestors punish by sending sickness or death, or by loss of property" (Bunzel, 1952:269).

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

Notes: "For the professions are sanctioned by the ancestors and any violation of their ethical code will be severely punished. Failure to make the required payments to the ancestors for the gift of ceremonies and for personal gain that may come through their exploitation may be punished by sickness or loss of money as a warning of worse to come if the offender does not mend his ways" (Bunzel, 1952:78).

↳ Done randomly:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating that supernatural punishment occurred randomly.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating that supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

Notes: See questions below for more information regarding supernatural punishment in this lifetime.

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Presumably, supernatural punishment in this life is highly emphasized due to the importance of ancestral spirits and honoring moral/ethical standards. Additionally, the principal ethnographic authority (Bunzel, 1952) does not describe supernatural punishment occurring in the afterlife.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:

– Yes

Notes: "Adultery, theft, drunkenness, and neglect of ritual obligations are other 'sins committed within the house' which the ancestors punish by sending sickness or death, or by loss of property" (Bunzel, 1952:269).

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: "Adultery, theft, drunkenness, and neglect of ritual obligations are other 'sins committed within the house' which the ancestors punish by sending sickness or death, or by loss of property" (Bunzel, 1952:269).

– Yes

Notes: "For the professions are sanctioned by the ancestors and any violation of their ethical code will be severely punished. Failure to make the required payments to the ancestors for the gift of ceremonies and for personal gain that may come through their exploitation may be punished by sickness or loss of money as a warning of worse to come if the offender does not mend his ways" (Bunzel, 1952: 78).

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– I don't know

Notes: Supernatural punishment is described in detail (see questions above). Prayers and rituals for supernatural protection are also described, but it is not clear whether supernatural beings are thought to bestow rewards.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– I don't know

Norms and Moral Realism

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: "For the professions are sanctioned by the ancestors and any violation of their ethical code will be severely punished" (Bunzel, 1952:78) "The Quichés believe that they live in a moral universe in which guilt never goes unpunished for long" (Bunzel, 1952:295).

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: "The powers whose influence on human affairs is continuous and unremitting are the ancestors, who represent the great moral force of the universe" (Bunzel, 1952:269).

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being:

– Yes

Notes: "For the professions are sanctioned by the ancestors and any violation of their ethical code will be severely punished" (Bunzel, 1952:78).

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating the presence of required celibacy.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating the presence of required castration.

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of required fasting.

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating the presence of required permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– I don't know

Notes: Regular prayer and ritual activities appear to occur, but it is unclear if the sacrifice of time is required for group membership. "On rising in the morning one crosses oneself, gives thanks to God for good health, and prays that one may remain in health two or three days, two or three months, two or three years" (Bunzel, 1952:15).

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– No

Notes: "It is usual, but not obligatory, before and after planting, and after harvest, to perform individual rites of thanksgiving for the land and the crops...But the most important seasonal ceremonies relating to agriculture are all fixed in the Catholic calendar. The optional ceremonies are performed if one has had bad luck, if one has performed no ceremonies for a long time, if one has omitted some obligatory ceremony, or if one has some secret sense of guilt" (Bunzel, 1952:56).

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– Yes

Notes: Although participation in large-scale rituals is not explicitly mandatory, these communal ceremonies and festivals are important to religious, social, and political aspects of K'iche' culture. "The calendar at Chichicastenango is full of fiestas which on the surface appear to be like all other Latin-American fiestas; they have all the usual earmarks - Masses, processions, fireworks, drinking, and dancing, sometimes large markets, and sometimes masked dances...But there are many features of Chichicastenango fiestas that are special to this village - the preliminary ceremonies, the ways of building climaxes, the peculiar social and political implications of the ferial system. A Quiché fiesta is a very complex phenomenon, both historically and functionally. It has many facets, and focuses many aspects of a complex social life...not all individuals participate to the same degree, nor in the same manner... Many come merely for pleasure, and some stay away because they have no money to spend, or are afraid of being trapped for work in the fincas" (Bunzel, 1952:192). Fiestas are described in detail in Bunzel, 1952, pp.192-254. See also Chapter 6, Rituals in Text Translations (pp.305-403).

On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– I don't know

Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of

governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Yes

Notes: "Of all the professions that of chuchqajau is the most important and the most highly formalized. The chuchqajau has supernatural powers; he is a diviner, sorcerer and mediator before the gods and the ancestors in all the crises of life. He is not, strictly speaking, a priest, for his relation to the supernatural is not such as to make his services in any ceremony indispensable. His position is that of an expert in occult science who performs ceremonies for others for pay" (Bunzel, 1952:79).

Is there use of intoxicants:

– Yes

Notes: Alcohol is described as present during fiestas and other communal ceremonies and festivals (see Bunzel, 1952:192-254).

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A chiefdom

Notes: The K'iche' had two levels of jurisdictional hierarchy beyond the local community, which is indicative of a chiefdom (Ethnographic Atlas column 33, Murdock, 1967; retrieved from Divale, 2004). For a detailed description of K'iche' government see Bunzel, 1952, Chapter Three: Government (pp.154-191).

Education

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: "The formal education of the child starts at about the age of eight...The government maintains a school in the village with two branches in the cantones" (Bunzel, 1952:105).

Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– I don't know

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 20, Food Storage, indicates that food is stored in individual households (Murdock

and Morrow, 1970; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Yes

Notes: "The administrative duties of the Principales de cantón [political authority in the cantone, or local district] concern levies of money and labor against the inhabitants and the appointment of minor officials. The only levies of money are those to defray the expenses of fiestas that are paid for by the pueblo - the Masses, candles, music for Holy Week, Corpus, and All Souls" (Bunzel, 1952:183).

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– Yes

Notes: According to Tuden and Marshall (1972) Column 10 (Police), "police functions are specialized and institutionalized on at least some level or levels of political integration."

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– Yes

Notes: According to Tuden and Marshall (1972) Column 9 (Judiciary) "supreme judicial authority is vested in a functionary or functionaries who are appointed by the supreme executive and/or the supreme deliberative body but are at least relatively independent of the appointing authority."

Written Language

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The Government school taught reading and writing in Spanish (see Bunzel, 1952:100).

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: See Bunzel, 1952, Appendix III: The Ecclesiastical Calendar at Chichicastenango

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Notes: The K'iche' relied predominantly on extensive or shifting agriculture. Animal husbandry supplemented the diet. Source of information: Ethnographic Atlas (Murdock, 1962-1971), retrieved from Divale, 2004; Variables 203-207, 232.

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Pastoralism

– Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards